

GreenComp-based Questionnaire (GCQuest) - ING

Questionnaire on the activity's contribution towards Education for Sustainability

This questionnaire aims to find out your opinion on the contribution of this activity to Education for Sustainability. The questionnaire is anonymous, and the data is processed for educational and scientific purposes only. It will take approximately 15 to 20 minutes to complete. There are no right or wrong answers. What matters is your opinion.

Thanks for your help!

A.1. Evaluation of the activity's contribution to Education for Sustainability

A.1.1. Considering the theme(s) of this activity, give 2 or 3 examples of something you have learnt.

A.1.2. Complete the following sentence: For me, Sustainability is...

A.1.3. Read each of the statements in the table carefully. All the statements complete the sentence: 'This activity allowed me to...'. The statements are intended to assess EduCITY's activity contribution to Education for Sustainability and have been adapted from 'GreenComp - European Competence Framework for Sustainability' for English version (available at: <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC128040>).

The response scale for each statement is between: 1 - 'Don't agree' and 6 - 'Agree'.

This activity allowed me to...	Response Scale					
	Disagree (1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	Agree (6)
... be prone to act in line with values and principles for sustainability.	<input type="radio"/>					
... articulate and negotiate sustainability values, principles and objectives while recognising different viewpoints.	<input type="radio"/>					
... identify processes or action that avoid or reduce the use of natural resources.	<input type="radio"/>					
... know that damaging and exhausting natural resources can lead to disasters and conflicts (e.g., loss of biodiversity, draughts, mass migration and war).	<input type="radio"/>					
... show empathy with all life forms.	<input type="radio"/>					
... evaluate issues and action based on sustainability values and principles.	<input type="radio"/>					
... be able to acknowledge cultural diversity within planetary limits.	<input type="radio"/>					
... be able to apply equity and justice for current and future generations as criteria for environmental preservation and the use of natural resources.	<input type="radio"/>					
... know about environmental justice, namely considering the interests and capabilities of other species and environmental ecosystems.	<input type="radio"/>					

This activity allowed me to...	Disagree						Agree
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	
... know the main views on sustainability: anthropocentrism (human-centric), technocentrism (technological solutions to ecological problems) and ecocentrism (nature-centred), and how they influence assumptions and arguments.	<input type="radio"/>						
... be committed to decreasing material consumption.	<input type="radio"/>						
... be able to bring personal choices and action in line with sustainability values and principles.	<input type="radio"/>						
... be willing to share and clarify views on sustainability values.	<input type="radio"/>						
... be able to find opportunities to spend time in nature and helps to restore it.	<input type="radio"/>						
... be able to see and imagine humans living together and respecting other life forms.	<input type="radio"/>						
... know that values and principles influence action that can damage, does not harm, restores or regenerates the environment.	<input type="radio"/>						
... care about a harmonious relationship existing between nature and humans.	<input type="radio"/>						
... respect, understand, and appreciate various cultures in relation to sustainability, including minority cultures, local and indigenous (from a region) traditions and knowledge systems.	<input type="radio"/>						
... be able to assess and question personal needs to carefully manage resources in the pursuit of longer-term goals and common interests.	<input type="radio"/>						
... be able to assess own impact on nature and consider the protection of nature an essential task for every individual.	<input type="radio"/>						
... know that individuals and communities differ in how and how much they can promote sustainability.	<input type="radio"/>						
... be able to help build consensus on sustainability in an inclusive manner.	<input type="radio"/>						
... be able to identify and include values of communities, including minorities, in problem framing and decision making on sustainability.	<input type="radio"/>						
... know that people are part of nature and that the divide between human and ecological systems is arbitrary.	<input type="radio"/>						
... be ready to critique and value various cultural contexts depending on their impact on sustainability.	<input type="radio"/>						

Thanks for your help!

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